

C-N Bond Activation and Ring Opening of a Saturated N-Heterocyclic Carbene by Lateral Alkali-Metal-Mediated Metalation

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Abstract: Combining alkali-metal-mediated metalation (AMMM) and N-heterocyclic carbene (NHC) chemistry, a novel C-N bond activation and ring-opening process is described for these increasingly important NHC molecules, which are generally considered robust ancillary ligands. Here, mechanistic investigations on reactions of saturated NHC SIMes (SIMes = [DC{N(2,4,6-Me₃C₆H₂)CH₂}₂]) with Group 1 alkyl bases suggest this destructive process is triggered by lateral metalation of the carbene. Exploiting co-complexation and trans-metal-trapping strategies with lower polarity organometallic reagents (Mg(CH₂SiMe₃)₂ and Al(TMP)iBu₂), key intermediates in this process have been isolated and structurally defined.

Since Arduengo's landmark isolation of the first N-heterocyclic carbene (NHC),^[1] an enormous amount of research activity has been devoted to advancing the applications of these special ligands, leading to important breakthroughs in transition-metal catalysis and organic synthesis^[2] as well as in main group chemistry.^[3] Many of these discoveries have been driven by the fine-tunability, relative stability and robustness of these molecules as strong two-electron sigma donors. Contrasting with the myriad of studies involving NHC-transition metal complexes,^[2] the use of these ligands in s-block metal chemistry has been limited to a few select investigations.^[4] Of these, key contributions from the groups of Arnold and Hill have demonstrated the excellent potential of NHCs for advancing s-block homogeneous catalysis,^[5] as well as for stabilizing novel Mg hydride clusters.^[6] Furthermore, the seminal work of Robinson^[7] on the deprotonation of IPr (1,3-bis(2,6-diisopropylphenyl)imidazole-2-ylidene) at its C4 position (alkenic backbone) with *n*BuLi has pushed forward the applications of anionic NHCs,^[8] opening up a new construction point for the functionalization of these ligands. Other examples of direct C4 metalation of unsaturated NHCs

have been reported using Na^[9] and K^[10] bases as well as mixed-metal systems such as sodium zincates^[11] or magnesiates.^[12] A novel example of this alkali-metal-mediated metalation (AMMM) involves the template base [Na₂Mg₂(TMP)₆(*n*Bu)₂] (TMP = 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidide), which simul-

taneously deprotonates the backbone of IPr along with one Dipp (Dipp = diisopropylphenyl) substituent at its *para*-position.^[12] Related to that finding, Braunstein has also described the unexpected lateral lithiation of a CH(Me)₂ wingtip of a Dipp in a 4-amido-substituted NHC.^[13] Surprisingly, despite all this recent activity, the metalation of dihydro saturated NHCs, containing non-aromatic C₃N₂ rings has hardly been touched upon, probably as a dual consequence of being less robust than their unsaturated congeners and having reduced acidity of their backbone hydrogen atoms. This has been nicely illustrated for the contrasting reactivities of IPr and its saturated analog SIPr when treated with lithium metal, with the former undergoing C4 metalation whereas the latter affords a ring-cleaved amidinate complex, although the mechanism of this reaction is unknown.^[14]

Breaking new ground, here, in reporting the first metalation study between a saturated carbene and alkali metal bases [MCH₂SiMe₃] (M = Li, K), we disclose a novel s-block metal-mediated activation process. Moreover, structurally mapping these reactions using SIMes (SIMes = [DC{N(2,4,6-Me₃C₆H₂)CH₂}₂]) as a case study, gives unique mechanistic insights into these transformations.

We started by reacting equimolar amounts of the silylalkyl reagents MR (M = Li, K; R = CH₂SiMe₃) with SIMes at room temperature, which gave oily solids. Adding donor ligands (one extra equivalent of SIMes and THF for M = Li and tridentate N-donor PMDETA for M = K, Scheme 1) allowed isolation of complexes 1 and 2 as crystalline products in 61 % and 66 % yields, respectively.

X-ray diffraction analysis of crystals of 1 and 2 revealed the presence of the same non-symmetrical amide ligand, containing mesityl and C₂H₄R arms, where R is a 1-indolyl substituent (Figure 1), presumably resulting from activation of neutral NHC SIMes. Reflecting the different coordination

Scheme 1. Reactions of SIMes with MCH₂SiMe₃ (M=Li, K).

Figure 1. Molecular structures of a) 1 and b) 2 with thermal ellipsoids at 30 % probability. Hydrogen atoms except for those attached to C37, C38, C2 and C3 in 1 and to C1 and C2 in 2 are omitted for clarity.

preferences of lithium and potassium, in 1 this amide ligand binds terminally to the metal via its amido N (N3 in Figure 1). Contrastingly, in 2, a chelating bonding mode is observed, where the K-N_{amide} bond is supported by a series of stabilizing π -electrostatic interactions with the indolyl C=C bonds, as well as with the C_{ipso} of the mesityl group. To engage in these ρ -contacts, K adopts a near perpendicular disposition to the planes defined by both aromatic rings. The coordination sphere of the alkali metals is completed by a THF molecule and one neutral SIMes ligand for 1, whereas in 2 K is chelated by tridentate PMDETA.

Although NHCs are generally accepted as robust spectator ligands, a number of studies have reported that when coordinated to transition metals they can undergo both C-H and C-N activation.^[15] To date, this reactivity has been missing in s-block chemistry, with the exception of HillQs^[16] work in the formal insertion of BeH₂ into a C-N bond of the unsaturated NHC IPr and the aforementioned reduction of SIPr with Li metal.^[14] The formation of 1 and 2 shows that under the conditions studied both alkali metal MCH₂SiMe₃ reagents are able to promote the cleavage of the SIMes C-N bond, that is significantly different from the reactivity observed when potassium bis(trimethyl)silyl amide is treated with unsaturated NHCs, where only donor-acceptor coordination of the NHC to the K center is observed.^[17] While as far as we can ascertain the activation of SIMes to give the anionic group present in 1 and 2 is unprecedented, it should be noted that investigations on other ring expanded carbenes containing *N*-mesityl substituents lead to the insertion of the carbene into one of their own *ortho*-methyl C-H bonds upon heating, furnishing *N*-alkyl indole products.^[18] Interestingly, the same studies have also reported the thermal resistance of SIMes to undergo insertion, even after prolonged periods of time (72 h at 70 °C).

In 1 and 2, the transformation of SIMes into the anionic amide N(Mes)(C₂H₄R) can be rationalized assuming that lateral metalation of one *ortho*-Me of its mesityl group occurs (II in Scheme 2). This transformation is probably favored by initial NHC pre-coordination to the alkali metal alkyl complex (I in Scheme 2). This will not only activate the organometallic reagent by reducing its aggregation,^[19] but will also bring the *ortho*-Me into close proximity to the reactive alkyl group, akin to the complex-induced proximity effect (CIPE) in directed *ortho*-metalation.^[20] As mentioned above, lateral deprotonations in NHC chemistry are extremely rare with only two examples described for unsaturated NHCs.^[12,14]

Scheme 2. Proposed mechanism for the formation of 1.

Notably, while these species are stable and can be structurally characterized, putative intermediate II must rapidly change to the ring-opened product III (Scheme 2), through the coupling of the benzylic CH₂ group of the mesityl substituent and the carbenic carbene, with subsequent cleavage of the C-N bond in the heterocycle to form III. This step resembles the mechanism proposed for ring expansion seen for NHC adducts of hydrosilanes and beryllium hydrides, where migration of anionic hydride to the electrophilic carbenic atom seems the rate-limiting step.^[21] Having H substituents adjacent to its carbenic site, III will not be stable^[22] and it will undergo a typical 1,2-hydrogen shift process,^[23] rearomatizing the five-membered ring, furnishing the *N*-alkyl indole fragment present in 1 and 2. Donor stabilization of IV (which in the case of M = Li is an additional equivalent of SIMes and THF) should lead to the crystalline products 1 and 2 (when M = K) (Scheme 2).

Attempts to isolate or even detect the postulated intermediates in Scheme 2 by reducing the temperature of the reaction were unsuccessful. Recently in collaboration with Mulvey we introduced the concept of trans-metal-trapping (TMT),^[24] where addition of low polarity organometallics such as Al or Ga species to lithiated substrates containing fragile anions allows stabilization and entrapment of these sensitive intermediates. Applying this approach to the lithiation of SIMes, we found that by using Mg(CH₂SiMe₃)₂ (0.5 equivalents) as an organometallic trap it is possible to intercept the postulated coordination adduct I (Scheme 2), which is isolated as the tetraorganomagnesiate 3 in a 56 % yield (Scheme 3). X-ray crystallographic studies confirmed the bimetallic Weiss motif^[25] constitution of 3 which can be envisaged as a co-complexation product of two equivalents of [SIMesLi(CH₂SiMe₃)] with one Mg(CH₂SiMe₃)₂ (Figure 2 a). Isolation of 3 implies that by forming a tetraalkylmagnesiate anion, containing significantly less polar and therefore less reactive metal-C bonds, the lateral metalation of SIMes is inhibited.

Scheme 3. Trans-metal-trapping (TMT) stabilizing strategies of reactive intermediates to give 3 and 4.

Figure 2. Molecular structures of a) 3 and b) 4 with thermal ellipsoids at 30 % probability. Hydrogen atoms except those attached to C2, C3, C23 and C24 in 3 and to C2, C3 and C20 in 4 are omitted for clarity.

In an attempt to trap the proposed metalated species prior to the ring-opening step we moved to the bimetallic combination LiTMP/Al(TMP)*i*Bu₂, where the steric mismatch between the two single-metal components precludes their co-complexation to form a lithium aluminate though they can still cooperate in a sequential manner to promote aluminatation of aromatic molecules.^[24] ¹H NMR monitoring of the reaction of SiMe₃ with LiTMP in deuterated THF^[26] demonstrated the formation of N(Mes)(C₂H₄R) amide fragment resulting from activation of the C-N bond in the carbene. On the other hand performing the same reaction in the presence of the aluminium trap [Al(TMP)*i*Bu₂] furnished lithium aluminate 4 in a 59 % yield (Scheme 3), whose molecular structure was determined by X-ray crystallographic studies (Figure 2 b).

Exhibiting a contacted ion pair structure, Li and Al are connected by an anionic SiMe₃ ligand, which has been

deprotonated at one *ortho*-Me of a mesityl ring, coordinating to Al via this benzylic C (C20 in Figure 2 b); whereas Li is attached to its normal carbenic position (C1 in Figure 2). The formation of 4 can be rationalized considering the fast transmetalation of the lateral lithiated intermediate II (Scheme 2) to the more carbophilic [Al(TMP)*i*Bu₂] fragment. Consistent with this interpretation, and illustrating the synergistic reactivity of this Li/Al bimetallic partnership, even when they operate in a non-synchronized manner, we found that on its own weak base [Al(TMP)*i*Bu₂] is unable to metalate SiMe₃. Notably, 4 is stable in C₆D₆ solutions at room temperature and no evolution to the C-N bond cleavage amide anion is observed over time.^[27] This stability can probably be attributed to the combination of the significantly greater covalent nature of the Al-C bond in 4 compared to the Li-C bond in the proposed lithium intermediate II, and the remote location of its benzylic position, sheltered by the bulky {Al(TMP)*i*Bu₂} fragment, with respect to the carbenic C [C20...C1, 3.701(5) c], which should also disfavor a possible intramolecular C-C coupling step.

While this lateral metalation of SiMe₃ is unprecedented, Aldridge has recently described intramolecular borylation at an *ortho*-Me group of an ancillary IMes ligand of an Ir complex using LiBH₄ as a boron source.^[15a] Interestingly, while from a mechanistic point of view, the formation of this C-H bond activation product is manifestly different to that of 4, as it involves an oxidative addition step via an Ir intermediate (in our case the + 1 oxidation state of the alkali metal is immutable), its structure shares several common features with that of 4. Thus this work builds bridges between two key areas in synthesis, namely transition-metal C-H activation and main group metal-mediated metalation.

Since 1 still contains a neutral SiMe₃ ligand coordinated to the Li center, we pondered whether it could be also activated. While an excess of LiCH₂SiMe₃ does not seem to be effective, the reaction with the heavier alkali metal alkyl KCH₂SiMe₃, led to the isolation of the novel mixed lithium/potassium complex 5 in 58 % yield (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4. Synthesis of potassium bis(amido) lithiate 5 via activation of the ancillary SiMe₃ ligand of 1.

The molecular structure of 5 displays two N(Mes)(C₂H₄R) anions coordinated to the lithium center via their N atoms, forming a novel potassium diamidolithiate complex (Figure 3). Contrastingly, K forms a series of p-K...C interactions, engaging in a h⁶-fashion with the mesityl fragments of the two amido ligands. These well-defined distinct bonding modes of Li and K contrast with those found in other mixed lithium/potassium amides such as [LiK(TMP)₂(PMDETA)] where both metals are bridged by amide N atoms.^[28] Potassium is further solvated by two molecules of THF while another THF completes the distorted trigonal

